

Cardiovascular Diseases in Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) Patients: A Cross-sectional Study

Authors:

Dr. Anita saibannavar¹, Dr. Vaibhav Mundhe²

¹Professor and head, dept of pulmonary medicine, R.C.S.M GMC, Kolhapur.

²PG student, R.C.S.M GMC, Kolhapur.

Corresponding Author:

Dr. Vaibhav Mundhe

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15830585>

Article Received: 15-May-2025, Revised: 05-June-2025, Accepted: 25-June-2025

ABSTRACT:

Background: Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) is a leading cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide, often accompanied by cardiovascular complications. This study evaluates cardiovascular manifestations in COPD patients and various risk factors for better outcome. **Methods:** A cross-sectional observational study was conducted at a tertiary care hospital in Maharashtra over 18 months. 100 COPD patients were assessed using history, clinical examination, electrocardiography (ECG), and echocardiography (ECHO). The presence of various cardiovascular manifestations and the associated risk factors were analysed. **Results:** The mean age of participants was 67.18 ± 9.38 years, with a male-to-female ratio of 44:56. Out of the total patients, 67% had a history of tobacco use, and 50% had biomass exposure. Hypertension (38%) was the most common comorbidity, followed by diabetes (5%). ECG findings revealed P-pulmonale (21%), ventricular premature contractions (12%), and atrial fibrillation (4%). ECHO findings showed Cor-pulmonale (33%), left ventricular hypertrophy (17%), and pulmonary arterial hypertension (9%). A significant association was found between cardiovascular manifestations and risk factors like tobacco use, type of respiratory failure, use of theophylline medications, and biomass exposure. **Conclusion:** COPD patients exhibit a high prevalence of cardiovascular abnormalities and severity of cardiovascular diseases increases with severity of COPD. With our study we emphasize on regular cardiovascular screening as it can improve patient outcome and will also reduce morbidity and mortality in COPD patients.

Keywords: COPD, Cardiovascular diseases, Cor-pulmonale, Arrhythmia, Pulmonary Hypertension.

INTRODUCTION:

Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) is a heterogenous lung condition characterized by chronic respiratory symptoms such as dyspnoea, cough, sputum production, and/exacerbations due to abnormalities of the airways (bronchitis, bronchiolitis) or alveoli (emphysema) that cause persistent and often progressive, airflow limitation¹. It is one of the most prevalent chronic diseases worldwide and is one of the leading causes of morbidity and mortality. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), COPD is now the third leading cause of death globally. Out of these, cardiovascular system involvement is a major cause of exacerbations, hospitalizations and increased duration of hospital stay². COPD is often associated with a variety of systemic effects, including cardiovascular complications, which have significant implications for patient outcomes. While the primary focus in COPD has been on the management of respiratory symptoms, increasing evidence points to the substantial impact of cardiovascular disease (CVD)

in this population. The systemic inflammation observed in COPD, combined with the mechanical strain exerted on the heart due to chronic hypoxia and altered lung mechanics, plays a critical role in the development of cardiovascular comorbidities. Studies have shown that cardiovascular events such as pulmonary hypertension, arrhythmias, left ventricular dysfunction, and right heart failure are more prevalent in COPD patients. One of the most significant cardiac manifestations in COPD patients is Cor-pulmonale, which refers to right-sided heart failure due to chronic pulmonary hypertension (PH) resulting from prolonged lung disease. Pulmonary hypertension and right ventricular hypertrophy are common findings in COPD patients and are associated with worsened prognosis and reduced exercise tolerance. Additionally, arrhythmias, including atrial fibrillation and ventricular arrhythmias, are frequently observed in COPD patients, with an increased risk of stroke and other cardiovascular complications. Furthermore, systemic inflammation and oxidative stress, which are

characteristic features of COPD, are believed to contribute to endothelial dysfunction, atherosclerosis, and accelerated aging of the cardiovascular system. Despite these well-documented associations, the exact mechanisms linking COPD to cardiovascular morbidity remain incompletely understood. This highlights the need for further research into the prevalence, pathophysiology, and outcomes of cardiovascular comorbidities in COPD patients. Given the significant overlap between COPD and cardiovascular diseases, clinicians must adopt an integrated diagnosis and management approach. However, the early detection of cardiovascular abnormalities remains a challenge due to the common overlap of respiratory and cardiovascular symptoms. Therefore, this study aims to assess the prevalence of cardiovascular manifestations in COPD patients, and to identify potential risk factors associated with these complications.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

An Observational, cross-sectional study was conducted at a Tertiary care hospital in Maharashtra for 18 months with a sample size of 100 COPD patients. Patients diagnosed with COPD and under treatment in the hospital and those willing to participate in the study were included. Patients with tuberculosis, or lung cancer, or cardiac arrhythmias or those unwilling to participate in the study were excluded. Patient demographic data, clinical examination findings, ECG, ECHO, cardiac biomarkers, and HRCT findings were recorded.

RESULTS:

Age: The mean age of the study subjects was 67.18 ± 9.38 years. The majority of participants were aged between 66 and 75 years, comprising 47% of the sample. The next largest age group was 56 to 65 years, which included 33% of the participants. A smaller proportion, 10%, were aged between 45 and 55 years. Individuals aged 76 to 95 years constituted 8% of the sample, while those older than 95 years made up only 2% (Figure 1).

Sex: The majority of subjects were female (56%) followed by male (44%)

Occupation: The majority of participants were farmers, comprising 53% of the sample. Housewives represented 28% of the participants. Other occupations included construction workers (5%), laborers (3%), and factory workers (2%). Various less-common occupations were also noted, including blacksmiths, police, and street food sellers, representing 1% of the sample.

Comorbidities: A significant proportion (42%), reported no comorbid conditions. Hypertension was prevalent among 38% of participants. The combination of hypertension and ischemic heart disease (IHD) was noted in 7% of participants, while 6% had both diabetes and hypertension. Diabetes alone was present

in 5% of the participants. A small number of participants had hypertension with chronic kidney disease (CKD), hypothyroidism each representing 1% of the sample (Figure 2).

History of tobacco use: Among study subjects, 67% of patients had a history of tobacco use whereas, it was absent in 33% of patients.

History of biomass exposure: Of the 100 participants, 50% had exposure to biomass (Household air pollution), 1% had exposure to wood dust, and 49% had no exposure.

Use of theophylline medications: A total of 92 patients reported to be using theophylline medications whereas, 8 participants had no use of theophylline medications.

Past exacerbation: A majority, 55%, reported experiencing past exacerbations, while 45% indicated they had not experienced any such events.

Duration of COPD symptoms: The largest proportion of participants, 34%, reported having symptoms for one year or less. This is followed by 26% with symptoms lasting between 2 to 5 years and 23% with symptoms spanning 6 to 10 years. A smaller percentage of participants reported longer durations, with 6% experiencing symptoms for 11 to 15 years, 9% for 16 to 20 years, and only 2% having symptoms for more than 20 years.

Type of respiratory failure: Type 1 respiratory failure was observed in 38% of the participants, while Type 2 respiratory failure was more prevalent, affecting 62% of the participants.

ECG findings: Out of 100 patients, 32% exhibited no ECG abnormalities. P-pulmonale was observed in 21% of the patients. Ventricular Premature Contractions (VPC) were identified 12% patients, while ischemic heart disease (IHD) was found in 9%. Both sinus arrhythmia and congestive cardiac failure (CCF) were detected in 5% of the total patients. Atrial Fibrillation (AF) was noted in 4%. Other findings included Left Axis Deviation (LAD) and Right Bundle Branch Block (RBBB), each present 3%. Less common findings included Left Ventricular Hypertrophy (LVH) and Mathews Syndrome (MAT) in 2% and 1% respectively, and S1, Q3, and T3 patterns as well as Acute Myocardial Infarction (MI), each observed in 1% of patients. (Figure 3).

2D ECHO findings: Cor-Pulmonale was the most prevalent condition, observed in 33% of patients, ECG was normal in 23% patients. Left Ventricular Hypertrophy (LVH) was identified in 17% patients, Pulmonary Arterial Hypertension (PAH) was noted in 9% patients, calcified aortic valve was found in 8 patients, Regional Wall Motion Abnormalities (RWMA) were present in 7% patients, Left Ventricular Hypokinesia was observed in 2%. Lastly, Aortic Regurgitation was recorded in 1%. (Figure 4).

Figure 1

Figure 4

Figure 2

Figure 3

DISCUSSION:

Cardiovascular diseases are common in COPD patients. Both conditions share common risk factors like smoking, air pollution and systemic inflammation. COPD is a multisystem disease involving cardiovascular complications such as hypertension, heart failure and ischemic heart disease. Chronic inflammation and oxidative stress in COPD can accelerate atherosclerosis and vascular dysfunction further worsening CVD. There are multiple risk factors pointing towards increased risk of CVD in COPD patients. But despite the increasing recognition of the significance of CVD in COPD³, still it is underdiagnosed and undertreated entity. Much of the existing epidemiological data has been derived from studies focused on specific patient groups, often those seen in secondary care settings with more advanced stages of the disease^{4,5}. This study aimed to evaluate cardiovascular manifestations in COPD patients within a tertiary care hospital, identify high-risk factors that contribute to these manifestations, and analyze the clinical-demographic characteristics of the patient population. The study revealed a significant prevalence of cardiovascular abnormalities among COPD patients, as evidenced by both ECG and ECHO findings. Approximately one-third of the patients (32%) had no ECG abnormalities, indicating that a significant proportion of COPD patients do not exhibit overt cardiac issues, despite the known association between COPD and cardiovascular disease. However, various cardiovascular conditions were identified in the remaining patients. P-pulmonale, a sign of right atrial enlargement, was the most common ECG abnormality, found in 21% of the cohort, reflecting the strain on the right heart often seen in COPD due to chronic hypoxia and pulmonary hypertension. VPC was observed in 12% of patients, suggesting a higher prevalence of arrhythmias in this population. IHD and sinus arrhythmia were present in 9% and 5% of patients, respectively, highlighting the cardiovascular burden in COPD patients. Other notable findings included AF in 4% and CCF in 5% of patients, emphasizing the diverse range of cardiovascular complications

associated with COPD. ECHO findings corroborated the ECG results, with Cor Pulmonale being the most prevalent condition, affecting 33% of the cohort. This aligns with the known pathophysiology of COPD, where chronic hypoxia leads to pulmonary hypertension and right heart strain. LVH was also significant, observed in 17% of patients, indicating potential systemic hypertension or increased cardiac workload. PAH was present in 9% of the cohort, further reflecting the pulmonary vascular complications of COPD. The study's findings are consistent with previous research. Garcia-Emmerich J et al. reported significant cardiac alterations in COPD patients, with right ventricle enlargement and pulmonary hypertension being common, similar to the current study's findings of Cor Pulmonale and PAH⁶. The study by Peter Alter et al. also found a high prevalence of cardiac comorbidities, particularly ischemic heart disease, and heart failure, which are echoed in the present study's findings of IHD and CCF⁷. Carter P et al. highlighted the independent association of COPD with various cardiovascular diseases, including heart failure and atrial fibrillation, supporting the present study's observation of these conditions in the COPD cohort⁸. The mean age of the study subjects was 67.18±9.38 years, with the majority aged between 66 and 75 years, which aligns with the known demographic distribution of COPD, where older age is associated with higher prevalence. However, it's notable that the cardiovascular manifestations observed in these patients were not significantly associated with age, despite age being a well-established risk factor for cardiovascular disease. This lack of association suggests that other factors, such as disease severity, duration, smoking history, and environmental exposures, may play a more critical role in the development of cardiovascular complications in COPD patients. The finding that 47% of the study population was between 66 and 75 years old reflects the cumulative impact of risk factors like long-term tobacco use, exposure to environmental pollutants, and the natural decline in lung function with age. The presence of cardiovascular manifestations across all age groups, including those younger than 65 years, highlights the complexity of the relationship between COPD and cardiovascular disease, where multiple risk factors interplay. Comparing these results with previous research, the systemic review mentioned indicates that COPD patients under 65 years old are particularly susceptible to cardiovascular complications, emphasizing the need for early intervention in this age group⁹. Curkendall et al.'s study on a Canadian cohort revealed a significant age-adjusted risk ratio for heart failure among COPD patients, reinforcing the connection between declining lung function and cardiovascular risk¹⁰. Similarly, Agarwal et al.'s findings from a US cohort demonstrated that lower FEV1 levels were linked to an increased incidence of heart failure, independent of

other risk factors, further underscoring the importance of lung function as a predictor of cardiovascular outcomes¹¹. Studies conducted using UK primary care data in particular have demonstrated that the relative risk of developing CVD associated with COPD is greatest in those in late-to-middle age¹². The majority of the study participants were female (56%), and although the distribution of cardiovascular manifestations did not show a statistically significant association with sex, it is important to consider gender differences in the clinical presentation and progression of both COPD and cardiovascular diseases. However, in this study, the lack of a significant association suggests that both sexes were equally susceptible to cardiovascular complications in the context of COPD. This finding is comparable with the study conducted by Yazici O et al¹³. A substantial proportion of participants had comorbidities, with hypertension being the most prevalent (38%). The coexistence of hypertension and ischemic heart disease was noted in 7% of participants, highlighting the intertwined nature of respiratory and cardiovascular health. A statistically significant association was found between hypertension and ECG or ECHO findings. A significant association was found between tobacco use and abnormal ECG findings ($P < 0.05$), underscoring the well-established link between tobacco exposure and cardiovascular disease. Tobacco use causes oxidative stress and inflammation, leading to endothelial dysfunction and atherosclerosis, which can manifest as various ECG abnormalities¹⁴. The study identified two types of respiratory failure among the participants; Type 1 (38%) and Type 2 (62%). While Type 2 respiratory failure was more prevalent and associated with more abnormal ECG findings, the difference was statistically significant. This suggests that while respiratory failure is a critical aspect of COPD, the type of respiratory failure may be a decisive factor in predicting ECG abnormalities. Similarly, a significant association between respiratory failure type and ECHO findings further supports the notion that cardiovascular manifestations in COPD patients are multifactorial and may be dependent on the type of respiratory compromise. The use of theophylline, a bronchodilator, was common among the participants, with 92% reporting its use. A significant association was found between its use and CVD. This may indicate that in this population, improper theophylline use significantly contributes to cardiovascular abnormalities especially arrhythmias¹⁵.

Conclusion: The study concluded that cardiovascular manifestations are prevalent among patients with COPD, highlighting the critical need for comprehensive cardiovascular evaluation in this population. A significant association was found between tobacco use, biomass exposure, hypertension, use of theophylline medications, type of respiratory failure underscoring the impact of these factors on cardiovascular health in COPD patients. While certain

risk factors play a crucial role in cardiovascular manifestations among COPD patients, other demographic and clinical factors may have a less direct influence. The results emphasize the importance of targeted interventions, to mitigate cardiovascular risks in COPD patients. The findings also emphasize the need for regular cardiovascular checkup among patients with COPD.

Acknowledgements:

I gratefully acknowledge the assistance provided by the staff. I am also thankful to the study participants for sharing the required information.

Conflicts of interests: None.

REFERENCES:

1. Celli B, Fabbri L, Criner G, et al. Definition and Nomenclature of Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease: Time for its Revision. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med* 2022.
2. Milne K, Sin DD. Acute Exacerbations of Chronic Lung Disease: Cardiac Considerations. *Cardiac Considerations in Chronic Lung Disease*. 2020 Jun 10:229–45. Doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-43435-9_12. PMID: PMC7282481
3. GOLD. Global Strategy for prevention, diagnosis and management of COPD: 2024 report. <https://goldcopd.org/2024-gold-report/> (accessed 21 August 2024).
4. Baty F, Putora PM, Isenring B, et al. Comorbidities and burden of COPD: a population- based case-control study. *PLoS One* 2013; 8: e63285.
5. Lange P, Mogelvang R, Marott JL, et al. Cardiovascular morbidity in COPD: a study of the general population. *COPD* 2011; 7: 5–10.
6. Garcia-aymerich J, Freixa X, Portillo K, Pare C, Gomez FP, Benet M, et al. patients with COPD at their first hospital admission. 2013;41(4):784–91.
7. Alter P, Barbara A, Kahnert K, Watz H, Biertz F, Bals R, et al. Prevalence of cardiac comorbidities, and their underdetection and contribution to exertional symptoms in COPD: results from the COSYCONET cohort. 2019;2163–72.
8. Carter P, Lagan J, Fortune C, Bhatt DL, Niven R, Chaudhuri N, et al. Association of Cardiovascular Disease with Respiratory Disease. 2019;73(17)
9. Morgan AD, Zakeri R, Quint JK. Defining the relationship between COPD and CVD: what are the implications for clinical practice? *Therapeutic advances in respiratory disease*. 2018 Jan 19; 12:1753465817750524.
10. Curkendall SM, DeLuise C, Jones JK, et al. cardiovascular disease in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease: Saskatchewan Canada cardiovascular disease in COPD patients. *Ann Epidemiol* 2006; 16: 63–70.
11. Agarwal SK, Heiss G, Barr RG, et al. Airflow obstruction, lung function, and risk of incident heart failure: the Atherosclerosis Risk in Communities (ARIC) study. *Eur J Heart Fail* 2012; 14: 414–422.
12. Feary JR, Rodrigues LC, Smith CJ, et al. Prevalence of major comorbidities in subjects with COPD and incidence of myocardial infarction and stroke: a comprehensive analysis using data from primary care. *Thorax* 2010; 65: 956–962.
13. Yazici O, Gulen ST, Eryilmaz U, Omurlu IK. The evaluation of cardiac functions according to chronic obstructive pulmonary disease groups. *The Aging Male*. 2020 Apr 2;23(2):106-111.
14. Hahad O, Kuntic M, Kuntic I, Daiber A, Münzel T. Tobacco smoking and vascular biology and function: evidence from human studies. *Pflugers Arch*. 2023 Jul;475(7):797-805. doi: 10.1007/s00424-023-02805-z. Epub 2023 Mar 24. PMID: 36961561; PMID: PMC10264470.
15. Ichikawa K, Wada T, Nishihara T, Tsuji M, Mori A, Yokohama F, Hasegawa D, Kawamoto K, Tanakaya M, Katyama Y, Sakuragi S, Ito H. A case of life-threatening supraventricular tachycardia storm associated with theophylline toxicity. *J Cardiol Cases*. 2017 Mar 6;15(4):125-128. doi: 10.1016/j.jccase.2016.12.004. PMID: 30279758; PMID: PMC6135038.